

Ocean Health Index Framework for Marine Food Security

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Abstract

Ocean health is vital for human and environmental survival. This research aims to design a framework for the application of the Ocean Health Index (OHI) in assessing water conditions, with a focus on the fisheries sub-sector for Food Provision purposes. Quantitative methods are used with the OHI+ approach which can be adapted to regional scales. The OHI assessment is carried out based on current status and short-term future status by considering trends, pressures and resilience from historical data of at least five years. This research found that fisheries status was assessed through biomass coefficient, sustainable fish stocks, and catch uncertainty. Environmental pressure factors include fishing gear, nutrient pollution and climate change, while social pressure is measured through the Worldwide Governance Indicators. Resilience is measured based on fisheries regulations and management. Results show that the OHI framework is effective in assessing ocean health and can be used as a guide for future regulatory design and strategic management.

Introduction

According to (Gaol, 2007) , biological resources in waters cannot be separated from the conditions and variations in oceanographic parameters. Apart from that, human activities without paying attention to the principles of sustainability and sustainability affect the availability of biological resources, so a balance is needed between ecological and human aspects (Akoit, 2018; Diposaptono, 2017) . Temperature and nutrient parameters are often used as determining indicators for water quality because they are susceptible to changes due to human activities and can threaten the survival of biota (Najamuddin *et al.* , 2020) . Ecological and human aspects of the sea also have a real

influence on the effectiveness of governance and regulations that must be implemented (Vierros, 2017) . Effective government governance and regulations are the main contribution to social integrity because they include social structures and internal community processes which are the foundation for economic and environmental progress (Sihotang, 2020). Measurement of the Ocean Health Index (OHI) can be carried out as an effort to monitor the use of marine resources. OHI is used to present information and water quality quantitatively from the perspective of human relations with the sea and contribute to sustainable development (Elfes *et al.* , 2014; Halpern, 2020; Halpern *et al.* , 2012; Ma *et al.* , 2016).

Healthy oceans in a sustainable manner provide various benefits for humans now and in the future (Halpern, 2020; Halpern *et al.* , 2012) . Marine health is defined as an ecosystem that has a balanced relationship between the ocean and humans (Wu, 2021). The Ocean Health Index (OHI) is a method introduced by Halpern *et al* (2012) for assessing and evaluating water conditions. OHI assesses ocean health based on the sustainable provision of benefits and services that people expect from a healthy ocean, such as food, cultural, social and employment values. In general, the OHI framework covers ecological-social relationships, aspects of marine use that can be used by humans, and sustainable use. The OHI framework has been used to assess the state of the ocean on a global, national and regional scale (Halpern *et al.* , 2012) . The global and national scale OHI is designed for the Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ) of countries or between countries as well as the entire global ocean, while the regional scale is designed to guide future assessments, regulatory design considerations, and strategic management of regions (Elfes *et al.* , 2014; Halpern *et al.* , 2014; Selig *et al.* , 2015) .

OHI assessment is rated on a scale of 0-100, a score of 100 indicates excellent management (Halpern *et al.* , 2012) . There are 10 objective areas assessed by this index. OHI assessments at global, national and regional scales contribute to sustainable development (Ma *et al.* , 2016). One of the objective areas in OHI+, namely food provision, can be used as an approach in determining conditions for the use of capture fisheries to monitor the use of fisheries that has been carried out in order to maintain resource sustainability. Therefore, the aim of this research is to design an OHI framework for providing food in the sea.

Method

The method used in this research is a quantitative method with the *Ocean Health Index* (OHI+) approach. This research focuses on assessing the Fisheries Sub-sector in the field of Food Provision *objectives* . OHI+ is used for small-scale assessments, such as regional, marine and gulf with variables that can be adjusted to the circumstances,

priorities, indicators and/or specifics of the region (Blenckner *et al.* , 2021; Elfes *et al.* , 2014; Team, 2018; W u *et al.* , 2021) .

The OHI framework carries out assessments based on current status (*present status*) and short-term future status (*future status*) from historical data (at least five years ago). These two statuses will each contribute a portion of the assessment of 50%. Current status is a combined value of the current conditions of each target area, while short-term future status is a combined value of *current* status , trend , pressure and *resilience* . The OHI+ calculation begins by determining the status of the target area and then determining the trend, pressure and resistance values as well as short-term future status.

Results and Discussion

The results of this research are shown in Figure 1

Figure 1. OHI framework for marine food security

Discussion

There are 7 data processes which are a combination of OHI+ calculations and oceanographic data processing.

Determination of Status Values from Fishery Data

Each goal has a different status determination (x_i) with a value scale of 0-100 (Halpern *et al.* , 2012) . Assessment of food supply objectives, fisheries aspects are

determined from capture fisheries data. The equation used in determining this value is as follows:

$$X_{FIS} = \left(1 - \frac{\delta B_T}{mMSY_R}\right) T_c \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Information:

- X_{FIS} : Assess fisheries status
- T_c : Species taxonomic quality data (can be assumed = 1, if taxonomic data per species is incomplete)
- δB_T : Landed biomass coefficient
- $mMSY_R$: Corrected multi-species sustainable fish stock (*multi-species maximum sustainable yield*).

The absolute difference δB_T is determined by

$$\delta B_T = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } |mMSY_R - B_T| < 0.05 \cdot mMSY_R \\ |mMSY_R - B_T| & \text{if } |mMSY_R - B_T| < mMSY_R \\ mMSY_R & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

With B_T is the size of the catch in the current year and $mMSY_R$ is determined to be 75% $mMSY$ to calculate the uncertainty of MSY between species, $mMSY_R = 0,75 * mMSY$. The value to $mMSY$ be obtained by adding up all the values of sustainable fish stocks (*maximum sustainable yield / MSY*) from each commodity landed, $mMSY = \sum MSY$.

MSY is the limit of the highest number of fish stocks that can be caught continuously without affecting the sustainability of fish resources (Rahim *et al.*, 2021; Taher *et al.* , 2020) . Calculation of MSY for each landed commodity is carried out using the *depletion-corrected average catch* (DCAC) method based on the Gulland and Alverson formula (MacCall, 2009) , this method is used in situations where there is a lack of catch data per species and fishing method. Equation used:

$$MSY = \frac{\sum C}{n + \left(\frac{w}{Y_{pot}}\right)} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Information:

- MSY : Sustainable fish stocks
- $\sum C$: Total fish catch in a certain time period
- n : Fish catch year (end year – start year+1)

$\frac{w}{Y_{pot}}$: Windfall ratio

Windfall ratio is a comparison value between the fishery results obtained and the potential results that can be harvested. This value is obtained by the equation:

$$\frac{w}{Y_{pot}} = \frac{\Delta}{0.4cM}; \Delta = \frac{B_{FYR} - B_{LYR}}{B} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Information:

- Δ : Changes in relative abundance of fish
- c : Adjustment coefficient (assumed = 1)
- M : Natural mortality rate / natural death rate of fish obtained from journal references (see Appendix 1)
- B_{FYR} : Abundance of catch in the first year
- B_{LYR} : Abundance of catches in recent years
- B : Average catch abundance

Trend Determination

Trend (T_i) is the slope value of the observed change in goal status (Halpern *et al.* , 2012) . The trend value of fisheries status can be determined by assessing changes in status , in this case the status from 2013 until 2021 with a value scale $-1 \leq T_i \leq 1$. Calculation of the slope of the linear regression line is used to determine the trend value, where year becomes the x variable while the status value becomes the y variable. Equation for calculating the slope of a linear regression line:

$$b = \frac{\sum(x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})}{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Information:

- b : Line slope (trend value)
- $\bar{x}; \bar{y}$: The average of each variable

Determination of Pressure Values

Stress is an ecological and social factor that can reduce goal status (Halpern *et al.* , 2012). The pressure value for each category will be different. Pressure values are divided into pressure originating from the environment (*Ecological Pressure*) and pressure originating from non-environment (*Social Pressure*). Pressure value calculation equation:

$$p_x = \gamma * p_E + (1 - \gamma) * p_S \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Information:

- p_x : The pressure value of a target area

γ : Relative weighting between p_E and p_S ($\gamma = 0.5$)

p_E : Ecological pressure

p_S : Social pressure

Ecological pressure plays a role in assessing the target area based on environmental factors that significantly influence the ecological state of a system. The division of categories, weights (w_i) and data parameters can be seen in Halpern (2012) and Table 3 shows the categories used in this research. There are 3 categories of ecological pressure, namely the use of fishing gear, nutrient pollution and climate change. The parameter contribution (p_i) to stress is scaled from 0 to 1, with 1 indicating the parameter contributes to ecological stress. Ecological pressure value calculation equation:

$$p_E = \frac{\sum(w_i * p_i)}{\sum w_i} \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

Table 1. Ecological Pressure Categories along with Data Weights and Parameters

Category	Weight	Data Parameters
Fishing Equipment	3	Gill net
Nutrient Pollution	1	Nitrate, Phosphate, DO
Climate change	1	Sea Surface Temperature (SST)

Note: weight 3 = high, 2 = medium, 1 = low

Social pressure describes the lack of effectiveness of government and social institutions (Halpern *et al.*, 2012). This value is determined from *the Worldwide Governance Indicators* (WGI) with measurements assessing 6 main indicator components. This component will be averaged, then rescaled from a range of -2.5 to 2.5 to a range of 0 to 1 using *Rescaling* (min-max normalization). Calculation equation:

$$x' = \frac{x - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)} \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

Oceanographic Data Processing and Analysis

Water conditions are determined based on physical (temperature) and chemical (nutrient) oceanographic data in the study area. Oceanographic data in the form of data on Sea Surface Temperature (SST), Phosphate (PO_4), Nitrate (NO_3), and Dissolved Oxygen (DO). SPL data is downloaded from *the Aqua Modis satellite* at <https://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/>, while PO_4 , NO_3 and DO data are downloaded from *the Copernicus Marine Service Information* (CMES) satellite at <https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/>. The step in processing oceanographic data in *ArcMap* 10.8 is to convert

oceanographic data which is in NetCDF (.nc) format into table data, then converted into .xls format to get better visualization in the form of graphs in *Microsoft Office Excel* .

After the visualization process is complete, the oceanographic data can be analyzed temporally to see the contribution of parameters to ecological pressure based on the increase in SST and water quality standards. Decree of the State Minister for the Environment Number 51 of 2004 concerning Sea Water Quality Standards for marine biota is used as a determinant of normal limits for nutrient parameters which can be seen in Table 4 .

Table 2. Sea Water Quality Standards for Marine Biota Based on Decree of the Minister of Environment Number 51 of 2004

No	Parameter	Quality standards
1	Phosphate	≤ 0.015 mg/l
2	Nitrate	≤ 0.008 mg/l
3	Dissolved Oxygen	>5 mg/l

Determination of Resilience Value

Resilience is an ecological factor and social agency (policy, law, etc.) that can reduce pressure on a goal (Halpern *et al.* , 2012) . The resilience component is divided into 3 measurement aspects, namely: ecological integrity (Y_E), goal-specific regulation in handling ecological pressure (G), and social resilience (Y_S). In calculating the future status in the field of food supply objectives, the parameters for calculating ecological integrity Y_E are not relevant (Halpern *et al.* , 2012) . Resistance value calculation equation:

$$r_x = \frac{G + Y_S}{2} \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

Determining specific regulatory objectives in this research uses policies and institutional actions that contribute to improving marine environmental management, thereby improving ocean health. The value G is obtained by the equation:

$$G = \frac{\sum w_i G_i}{\sum w_i} \dots\dots\dots (10)$$

Referring to Halpern (2012), the regulations and weights used are fisheries resilience version 1 with parameter weights divided equally from the total weight 2, which can be seen in Table 5 and the value of $G_i = 1$ for the availability of related regulations.

Table 3. Weight distribution in P arameters analyzed for Resilience Version 1

Fisheries Resilience	Weight (w_i)
CBD (<i>convention on biological diversity</i>)	0.67
MPA (<i>Marine Protected Area</i>)	0.67
Effectiveness of fisheries management	0.67

Social resilience (Y_s) is described as the internal processes of an area that influence resilience (Halpern *et al.* , 2012) . In this research, data from WGI with an average calculation of 6 components determines this value variable.

Determination of Short-Term Future State Value

The short-term future status value of a category is estimated as a function of 4 dimensions: current status, current trends (past 5 years), cumulative ecological and social pressures, and resilience. The value of the future state is defined as:

$$x_{iF} = (1 + \delta)^{-1} [1 + \beta T_i + (1 - \beta)(r_x - p_x)] x_i \dots\dots\dots(1\ 1)$$

Information

- x_{iF} : Future state value
- δ : Weighting truncation (set = 0)
- β : Represents the relative importance between trend and stress-resistance ($\beta=0.67$)
- T_i : Trend Value
- r_x : The value of resilience
- p_x : The value of the pressure
- x_i : The value of the goal state

The value β is assumed to be 0.67 as an indicator of a better estimate of future conditions (5 years) (Halpern *et al.* , 2012) .

Determining the Value of Food Provision Objective Fields

The average result of the current fisheries status (X_{FIS}) with the short-term future status (X_{iF}). The index value (I) is determined by the equation:

$$I = \frac{X_{FIS} + X_{iF}}{2} \dots\dots\dots(1\ 2)$$

Conclusion

This research succeeded in designing a framework for the application of the Ocean Health Index (OHI) which can be applied on a regional scale with a focus on the fisheries sub-sector for Food Provision purposes. Through a quantitative approach and historical data analysis, the OHI+ method is proven to be effective in assessing ocean health conditions based on current and future status, as well as considering factors such as trends, pressure and resilience. Assessments show that ocean health is strongly influenced by human activities and environmental factors such as fishing gear, nutrient pollution, and climate change. This research also highlights the importance of effective fisheries regulation and management to increase marine resilience. The results obtained can be used as a guide for creating better policies and management strategies for the sustainability of marine ecosystems and the provision of sustainable benefits for society.

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Disclaimer

This research is part of Arnisa Selvi's final assignment. The framework for this research is a concept from Ankiq Taofiqurohman, which was perfected by Arnisa Selvi.